

Why Music Is Capable of Inducing Changes in Gene Expression in Cancer Cells

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Abstract: Recently, some scientists have argued that music can have direct effect on gene expression in cancer cells. We confirm their results and show that music induce its changes through two ways. In one method, music waves are taken by auditory system, converted into electrochemical signals within Cochlear and transformed into auditory cortex. Then, by exchanging waves between neural circuits within auditory cortex and Hypothalamus, some GnRH hormones are produced which their actions on Pituitary lead to production of LH and FSH hormones. These hormones force into Ovary and Testis for creating Estrogen, Testosterone and Progesterone. Estrogen is taken by receptors on the cell membrane, transformed into the nucleus and contributes in gene expression. In second method, music waves are taken by liquids within blood vessels and other systems and transformed into liquids out of cells. These waves make a pressure on cell membranes and produce an unbalance conditions between inside and outside of cells. This causes to the motions of charged particles through gates, production some electrical and mechanical currents and emergence of shorter wavelength longitudinal and transverse electromagnetic (EM) waves. EM waves pass the nuclear pores and enter into nucleus. Longitudinal waves make a second pressure on the nuclear membrane, cause to motion of ions and charged particles and creation of very shorter wavelength longitudinal and transverse EM waves. These waves could guide various types of polymerases like RNA Polymerase and DNA polymerase to their binding sites or act like the repressors and have the main role in transcription, translation and replication. Using these waves, we can control gene expressions in cancer cells. We test the model on chick embryos and find that music waves increase the growth rate of cells.

I.Introduction

Up to date, many investigations on music therapy and music medicine have been done and various methods have been proposed. For example, in one

research, authors have compared the impact of music therapy (MT) versus music medicine (MM) interventions on psychological outcomes and pain in cancer patients and to enhance understanding of patients' experiences of these two types of music interventions [1]. In another investigation, authors have indicated that music interventions may have beneficial effects on anxiety, pain, fatigue and QoL in people with cancer. Furthermore, music may have a small effect on heart rate, respiratory rate and blood pressure [2]. In another paper, investigators have shown that music therapy and progressive muscle relaxation training can reduce depression, anxiety and length of hospital stay in female breast cancer patients after radical mastectomy [3]. In another work, researchers have found that Music-based interventions have positive effects on cancer patients' anxiety, depression, pain, life quality of life. They have shown that greater reductions of anxiety and depression can be observed in breast cancer [4]. Another research has explored the effects of music therapy on self-reported symptoms of patients receiving inpatient care at a comprehensive cancer center. It has been shown that a single, in-person, tailored music therapy intervention as part of an integrative oncology inpatient consultation service contributed to the significant improvement in global, physical, and psychosocial distress [5]. Other researchers have shown that individual music therapy sessions may be effective to reduce fatigue related to cancer and symptoms of depression, as well as to improve quality of life for women with breast or gynecological cancer undergoing radiotherapy [6]. Also, another investigators have considered effects of music therapy on mood and pain with patients hospitalized for bone marrow transplantation. They have shown that although no result was significant, there were positive changes resultant of patient-preferred live music in pain, relaxed/anxious, wide awake/drowsy, and cheerful/depressed in the experimental group [7]. And in one of newest works, authors have demonstrated music as a modulator of gene expression in a cancer cell line [8]. Now, the question arises that how long wavelength of music waves could have the role in controlling gene expression? In this paper, we response this question and show that music waves induce shorter wavelength waves within the nucleus and then these second high energetic waves control repressors, Polymerases and other transcription, translation and replication factors in gene expression.

The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, we propose two methods for transferring effects of music waves to nucleoplasm and controlling gene

expression. In section III, we consider the effect of music waves on the growth of cells in a chick embryo. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

III. Music waves could control Gene expression in cells

In this section, we propose two mechanisms which Music waves could contribute in Gene expressions. We show that these waves have direct effects on transcription, translation and replication. These mechanisms are:

1. Music waves could enter into auditory system, move hairs within Cochlear and produce electrochemical signals. These waves move through neurons and achieve to auditory cortex within the brain [9]. Then, they can be exchanged between neural circuits of brain and achieve to Hypothalamus. Due to effects of these waves, Hypothalamus produce GnRH hormones which force into Pituitary for producing FSH and LH hormones [10,11]. These hormones go to Ovary in females and Testis in males and cause to creation of Estrogen, Progesterone and Testosterone [12]. Estrogen is taken by special receptors on cell and nucleus membranes and contribute in gene expression (See figure 1).

Fig 1. Music waves contributes in gene expression by producing various types of hormones

- Music waves lead to motions of ions and charged particles within the blood vessels and production of longitudinal waves. According to laws of physics, by motion of charged particles, some EM waves are emerged. These waves could enter into neurons and be transformed to neural circuits of brain . Consequently, they can force into Hypothalamus and produce hormones (See figure 2).

Fig 2: Music waves move charged particles within the blood cells and produce longitudinal and EM waves

Some of Music waves produce longitudinal waves within the liquids of blood vessels and liquids around cells. These waves make a pressure to cell membrane and produce unbalanced medium. To achieve to stable medium, charged particles move through membrane gates and produce some shorter wavelength waves within the cell. Also, by motion of charged particles, a current is emerged which emit some electromagnetic waves (See figure 3).

Fig 3. Music waves produce longitudinal and transverse within the cells

Some of longitudinal waves within the cells, make a new pressure to nuclear membrane and make an unbalanced medium around nucleus. This unstable conditions lead to the motion of charged particles and emergence of some strong currents. These currents produce some high energetic longitudinal and transverse waves with very short wavelength and pass nuclear pores (See figure 4).

Fig 4: Music waves produce short wavelength waves within nucleus.

Longitudinal and transverse waves within the nucleus, contribute in gene expression. For example, short wavelength longitudinal waves force into RNA polymerase and guide them to promoter region or prevent them from attaching to these regions. In parallel, transverse waves could cover promoter region and repel or absorb RNA polymerases (See Figure 5).

Fig 5: Music waves control behavior of RNA Polymerase

During transcription, longitudinal and transverse waves could force into molecules for entering to RNA polymerase and contributing in transcription process. In some conditions, they can prevent of entering material to Polymerases and cause to stop process (See Figure 6).

Fig 6: Music waves contribute in transcription process

During translation process within the nucleus, longitudinal waves could force into transfer RNA and Ribosomal subunits to sit down on starting codons. Also, transverse waves could cover starting codons and absorb or repel Ribosomal subunit and transfer RNA. Thus, these waves control process of translation from begging to end (See Figure 7).

Fig 7: Music waves control behavior of transfer RNAs and Ribosoms during translation

During replication, longitudinal and transverse waves could guide Helicase to sit down on related binding site and begin process of separating base pairs. Also, these waves locate Primase on related site to produce primer. After that these waves control behavior of DNA polymerase and guide it for sitting down on DNA strands and constructing extra strands. Thus, these waves could accelerate or decelerate the process of replication and increase or decrease number of cells. This helps us to control behavior of cancer cells (See figure 8).

Fig 8. Music waves guide DNA polymerase to primers during replication

III. Effect of Music waves on gene expression within the cells of chick embryos

To consider effects of music waves on gene expression and growth rate of cells, we use of shell-less culture systems [13,14]. To this aim, we provide some chick embryos out of shell (shell-less culture). We pour some amount of water in some vessels or tubes and put a plastic on it. Then, we break a group of eggs, pour them on the plastic and create some small holes such as molecules of water could evaporate and provide needed wet for egg cells. Next, we put another plastic on the head of tubes or vessels. We connect vessels to an scope like Radio-Skypipe and Amperemeter to measure changes in emitted electromagnetic waves and produced currents. We put vessels into an incubator and keep them at 38⁰ C for 120 h (See Figure 9). We divide cells into two groups. We expose first group of cells to music waves and consider their growth

rate. Then, we consider the behavior of second group of cells without exposing to music waves and compare with the behavior of first group. We observe that growth rate of cells which are exposed to Music waves is more than growth rate of cells without playing any music. It is concluded that Music waves contribute in gene expression and accelerate the process of formation of new cells (See figure 10).

Fig 9: A setup for considering the effect of Music waves on the growth rate of cells within the chick embryos

Fig 10. Growth rate of chick embryos (Red color corresponded to exposing cells to music waves and blue color without any music)

Conclusion

Newly, some investigators have evaluated the effect of music on proliferation and gene expression in gastric cancer cells experimentally [8]. We have proposed some theoretical reasons for these results and controlling gene expression by music waves. We have shown that music waves have two different effects on biological systems. They can be converted into electrical and chemical signals by hairs within Cochlear, move through neurons and achieve to auditory cortex. Then, these waves are exchanged between neural circuits within the brain, enter into Hypothalamus and produce GnRH. This hormone forces Pituitary to produce LH and FSH and these hormones make a pressure on Ovary and Testis to create Testosterone and Progesterone. These hormones are absorbed by cells, enter into their nucleus and contribute in gene expression. In parallel, music waves can induce some longitudinal waves in liquids within blood vessels. These waves achieve to cell membranes, make a pressure on them and produce some shorter wavelength longitudinal waves. These waves lead to the motion of charged particles and create some EM waves. Also, these waves make a pressure on nuclear membranes, produce second type of longitudinal waves with shorter wavelength and EM waves. These waves control motions and behavior of RNA and DNA Polymerases and control gene expressions. To consider the effect of music waves on gene expressions, we compare growth rate of cells within the chick embryos for two states, one by exposing cells to metal and classical music and second without any music. We have observed that music waves accelerate the growth of cells and thus, the model works.

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